

Review form: Impulse funding Open Science Communities-NL

Reviewer 1:

Concrete and realistic project plan

Please elaborate if the project plan is sufficiently concrete and realistic to achieve the intended four objectives 1) networking, 2) knowledge management, 3) increasing visibility and findability and 4) organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period.

This evaluation criterion refers to the application as a whole.

Please comment

The intention to host the OSC-NL ET within SURF provides an excellent opportunity to benefit from the co-location of other relevant organisations and events, and also acts a venue for meetings. It supports 1) networking 3) increasing visibility and findability and 4) organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project.

(A minor point – the numbering in the GANT chart of the deliverables on page 4 does not correspond to the numbering in the text.)

The concept of developing a toolkit for different aspects of the OSC is solid - presumably this will be targeted at the people who are currently volunteering their time to manage the OSC communities? If the intention is to keep these people on with reimbursement for 0,2FTE then this would allow time for the intended OSC incubator program over 12 weeks. Otherwise it is not clear how the community managers would be able to find the time to do the program as well as run their community.

Workplan 1.2.1 is dependent on members of the OSC-NL Board having the expertise and the available time to serve on the boards listed.

It is not clear what 'PM' means – I am assuming 'person month'? I have not assessed the time allocated to each of the workplans to determine if these are a realistic allocation of time.

The Workplan 3 might need to consider the time-hungry nature of developing communication resources, the apparent allocation of time from WP3.1 seems too low.

The sustainability plan is slated to be developed in year 3 and then finalised in year 4, but this will presumably need to be completed early in year 4 in order to begin enacting the plan. It is not sustainable to wait until the funding has finished before starting the plan.

Team composition

Please assess if the team composition described in the application in your opinion is appropriate for carrying out the work of OSC-NL.

This assessment is based on the description of the proposed Executive Team as provided in the application. There are two questions that arise:

1. The way the application is written suggests there is no competitive process for identifying the members of the Executive Team. If there has been a previous process undertaken in order to identify these people, this should be included in the application. If there has not been a process then it is possible this could be a point of concern later for the Open Science NL Steering Committee.
2. There is currently no assurance in the application that the people nominated for the Executive Team are able to be released from their current roles. Are we assuming that Jet de Ranitz's signature approves the in-kind time of Tanya van Goch. Melanie Imming works as a consultant yet is providing in-kind time to the project.

There is a high level of financial responsibility falling on Rianne Fijten who is looking after 4.2.1, 4.2.2 and 4.2.3. It is not clear from the short description that there is sufficient financial or fundraising expertise to meet this workload.

On page 2 there is mention of the need to reimburse existing local community managers for ca. 0,2 FTE. The application does not indicate if that commitment is expected to continue once the Executive Team is established.

Relevant target groups and resources

To what extent are relevant target groups and resources described in the application form? Are the resources appropriate to reach these target groups?

This evaluation criterion refers to the description of reaching the goal "Increase visibility and findability of local Open Science Communities and open science expertise" in the application form. Here the applicant is asked to describe target groups the network currently addresses, and which target groups may still be missing, as well as specifying which communication channels (such as website, newsletters, events, etc.) are already available to the network now and which need to be (further) developed.

The proposal describes mechanisms to further engage existing OSC Community Managers and a plan to introduce some further organisations. There is a challenge with this type of community activity that a large amount of knowledge and momentum can lie with individuals who can move roles. The proposal describes some solid mechanisms to embed systems and processes to assist with the onboarding of new people into these roles.

In terms of resources, there is an allocation of EUR 8.000 for the development and hosting of websites. If the organisation is not successful in managing sustainability beyond this initial four years, what is the contingency plan for ensuring the resources developed are being preserved somewhere once the hosting payments cease?

The travel budget equates to EUR312 per person per year. This would be sufficient to cover train travel across the Netherlands but not any hotel stays. Is it sufficient? Given the reimbursement fund for members of OSC-NL members or external people is EUR11.000 for the same period there seems to be a discrepancy.

Organisational embedding and sustainability

Please comment if the organisational embedding is sufficiently appropriate for the project plan. Does the application describe realistic steps to perpetuate the network? Note, that the applicant is asked to describe how OSC-NL is (or can be) built up organisationally (type of governance) and which steps OSC-NL could take to perpetuate the network after the end of the project period. At this stage the applicant is not asked for a definite answer. Steps towards

sustainability are part of the annual reporting to Open Science NL.

This evaluation criterion refers to the 'Organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period (sustainability)' section of application form.

The primary embedding will be the locating of the Executive Team in SURF which will contribute greatly to this evaluation criteria.

The perpetuation of the network beyond social media presence will primarily be contained in workplans 2.2.1 and 2.4.

Workplan 2.2.1 is a little vague – is there an intention to hold an annual knowledge exchange? The description does not provide a cadence. These types of events are incredibly useful for the purposes of developing a community of practice and progressing discussions. However if these will be held in person, then careful management of the travel budget will be required.

There is some cross over with Workplan 2.4 which describes people meeting up and sharing knowledge and inspire each other. Perhaps some innovation could be addressed to ensure there is not a double-up of effort – Loek and Melanie will need to work closely together on these.

Summary of your assessment

Overall evaluation of the application

Please describe if you find the application of sufficient quality to receive funding from Open Science NL. Please note that an application of good-enough quality is seen eligible for funding from Open Science NL and the application does not get the opportunity to re-submit an adjusted application form.

Please comment on your overall decision.

Generally this seems like a good proposal. The types of activities that have been proposed seem to be sensible and should encourage the outcome sought by the project. I have not undertaken a complete analysis of the allocated time (and therefore funds) for each of the workplans. I feel the amount of time that seems to be allocated to communication is likely to be insufficient, for example.

The proposal for events and knowledge exchanges is a good one, these are proven to be effective. However, even if the meeting location is able to be secured at SURF without cost to the project, there is no budget for catering. I am also concerned the travel budget is too tight.

This proposal is most decidedly 'good enough'. Once the work begins, the Executive Team will have a more realistic idea of how their time will be able to be allocated. Something that does need addressing by NOW is ensuring the outputs of this project are able to be preserved and shared after the project has completed even if there is not ongoing work.

I look forward to seeing the outcomes of the work of the OSC-NL.